

ON THE SYMMETRY GRAPH OF PRIME NUMBERS

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alkalb1995cd@mail.ru*Received: 12/4/19, Revised: 6/24/20, Accepted: 12/14/20, Published: 1/4/21***Abstract**

A pair $\{p, q\}$ of odd primes is called symmetric if $|p - q| = (p - 1, q - 1)$. The symmetry graph of primes is the graph whose vertices are primes and there is an edge between p and q if and only if $\{p, q\}$ is a symmetric pair. In this paper we partially answer some questions regarding properties of the symmetry graph of primes stated in a recent article by W. Banks, P. Pollack and C. Pomerance. In particular, we provide an explicit example of a connected component of this graph that has two vertices, and prove that Dickson's conjecture implies the existence of connected components isomorphic to a given finite connected graph.

1. Introduction

A pair of distinct odd primes $\{p, q\}$ is said to be symmetric if $(p - 1, q - 1) = |p - q|$. Primes that are members of at least one symmetric pair are symmetric and all other primes are asymmetric. Properties of the set of symmetric primes are studied in the papers [1] and [2]. The first paper also contains several questions on the symmetry graph of prime numbers. This graph is defined as follows: the vertices are odd primes, and two primes p and q are connected by an edge if $\{p, q\}$ is a symmetric pair. In this note we will denote the symmetry graph of primes by \mathcal{G} . As the most interesting part of \mathcal{G} contains only symmetric primes as vertices, we denote by \mathcal{G}^+ the symmetry graph of symmetric primes. Three of the questions in article [1] can be reformulated as follows:

Question 1. Is \mathcal{G}^+ connected?

Question 2. If the answer to Question 1 is “no”, then what is the least symmetric prime that is not in the connected component of 3?

Question 3. Does the graph \mathcal{G}^+ contain infinitely many components?

Here we are going to give partial answers to these questions.

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2. Questions 1 and 2

Our first result is of numerical nature.

Theorem 1. *The graph \mathcal{G}^+ is not connected and the least prime that is not in the connected component of 3 is less than or equal to 3343.*

Proof. Indeed, $3343 - 1 = 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 557$, so 3343 can only be connected with $3343 \pm 2, 3343 \pm 6, 3343 \pm 1114, 3343 \pm 3342$. Only one of these numbers, namely $3343 + 1114 = 4457$, is prime, because

$$3343 + 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, 3343 - 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{13},$$

$$3343 - 1114 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, 3343 + 3342 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$$

and $3343 - 3342 = 1$, which is not prime. Now, $4457 - 1 = 2^3 \cdot 557$, so it can only be connected with $4457 \pm 2, 4457 \pm 4, 4457 \pm 8, 4457 \pm 1114, 4457 \pm 2228$ or 4457 ± 4456 . On the other hand, we have

$$4457 - 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, 4457 + 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{7}, 4457 - 4 = 61 \cdot 73,$$

$$4457 + 4 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, 4457 + 8 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, 4457 - 8 \equiv 0 \pmod{3},$$

$4457 + 1114 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, 4457 - 2228 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, 4457 + 2228 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, 4457 + 4456 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and finally $4457 - 4456 = 1$, which is not prime. This means that 3343 is connected only to 4457 and 4457 is connected only to 3343, which makes $\{3343, 4457\}$ a connected component of the graph \mathcal{G}^+ . This completes the proof of Theorem 1. \square

Remark 1. Further computations show that 3343 is, in fact, the least symmetric prime that is not connected to 3.

3. Question 3

Here we prove, assuming the truth of certain asymptotic form of Dickson's conjecture, that \mathcal{G}^+ does, indeed, have infinitely many connected components. In fact, we will prove that for any finite connected graph \mathbb{G} there are infinitely many connected components of \mathcal{G}^+ that are isomorphic to \mathbb{G} . First of all, let us formulate the conjecture we will rely on.

Conjecture 1. If a_1, \dots, a_n are distinct positive integers such that for any prime number p the polynomial $x(a_1x + 1) \dots (a_nx + 1)$ has less than p roots modulo p , then there are constants $x(\mathbf{a})$ and $C(\mathbf{a}) > 0$ such that for $x > x(\mathbf{a})$ we have

$$\#\{m \leq x : m, a_1m + 1, a_2m + 1, \dots, a_nm + 1 \text{ are primes}\} \geq \frac{C(\mathbf{a})x}{(\ln x)^{n+1}}.$$

Theorem 2. *If Conjecture 1 is true, then for any finite connected graph \mathbb{G} there are infinitely many connected components of \mathcal{G}^+ that are isomorphic to \mathbb{G} .*

This result can be easily deduced from the following lemma on induced subgraphs in the symmetry graph of positive integers.

Lemma 1. *Let Z be the graph whose vertices are positive integers and two integers n and m are connected with an edge if $(n, m) = |n - m|$. Then for any finite connected graph \mathbb{G} there exists an induced subgraph of Z isomorphic to \mathbb{G} .*

Let us show that Theorem 2 follows from Lemma 1.

Proof of Theorem 2 assuming Lemma 1. Let \mathbb{G} be our finite connected graph on N vertices and a_1, \dots, a_N be the set of distinct positive integers such that corresponding induced subgraph is isomorphic to \mathbb{G} . Note that the same property also holds for the set $A_1 = (N + 1)!a_1, \dots, A_N = (N + 1)!a_N$ and this set satisfies the condition of Conjecture 1, since the corresponding polynomial cannot have more than $N + 1$ roots and has only one root $x = 0$ modulo p for $p \leq N + 1$. If Conjecture 1 is true, then there are at least $\frac{C(\mathbf{A})x}{(\ln x)^{N+1}}$ integers $m \leq x$ such that m is prime and the numbers $A_i m + 1$ are prime for all $1 \leq i \leq N$. For every such m , the induced subgraph of \mathcal{G}^+ on vertices $\{A_i m + 1, i \leq N\}$ is isomorphic to \mathbb{G} , because $(A_i m, A_j m) = |A_i - A_j| m$ if and only if $(A_i, A_j) = |A_i - A_j|$. Let us show that for almost all m with abovementioned property this subgraph is in fact a connected component. Indeed, $A_i m + 1$ can only be connected with $(A_i \pm d_i)m + 1$ and $A_i m + 1 \pm d_i$, where $d_i \mid A_i$. Therefore, if the constructed subgraph is not a connected component, then there is at least one edge that goes outside the set $\{A_i m + 1, i \leq N\}$, which means that at least $N + 2$ values of different linear forms from the set $\{m, A_i m + 1, (A_i \pm d_i)m + 1, A_i m + 1 \pm d_i\}$ are prime. There are only $O(1)$ possible choices for $N + 2$ forms and for each choice there are at most $O(x(\ln x)^{-N-2})$ such values of $m \leq x$ (see [3], Section 2.6). So, for most m we get the connected component of \mathcal{G}^+ that is isomorphic to \mathbb{G} , as needed. \square

So, all we need to do now is to prove Lemma 1. Let us first introduce a new definition.

Definition 1. The set $\{a_1, \dots, a_N\}$ is called strongly symmetric if $(a_i, a_j) = |a_i - a_j|$ and for all $i > j$ there exist a prime p and $m \geq 1$ such that $p^m \mid a_i - a_j$ but $p^m \nmid a_k - a_l$ if $k > l$ and $(k, l) \neq (i, j)$.

For example, the set $\{30, 36, 45\}$ is strongly symmetric, because $(30, 45) = 15 = 45 - 30$, $(36, 45) = 9 = 45 - 36$, $(30, 36) = 6 = 36 - 30$ and also 15 is divisible by 5, 9 is divisible by 3^2 and 6 is divisible by 2.

Remark 2. Choosing m to always be as large as possible, we can also guarantee that p^{m+1} does not divide $a_i - a_j$.

In our next lemma we show that there are arbitrarily large strongly symmetric sets.

Lemma 2. *For any N there exists a strongly symmetric set of cardinality N .*

Proof. Notice first that one can multiply a strongly symmetric set by any positive integer and shift a strongly symmetric set by any positive common multiple of its members without breaking the strong symmetry condition. Indeed, if $\{a_1, \dots, a_N\}$ is strongly symmetric, then for any r and any $i > j$ we have

$$(ra_i, ra_j) = r(a_i, a_j) = r|a_i - a_j| = |ra_i - ra_j|$$

and $p^{m+\alpha} \mid r(a_i - a_j)$, but $p^{m+\alpha} \nmid r(a_k - a_l)$ if $k > l$ and $(k, l) \neq (i, j)$, where p^α is the largest power of p that divides r . On the other hand, if a is a positive common multiple of a_1, \dots, a_N then $a_1 + a, \dots, a_N + a$ has the same set of differences and also

$$(a_i + a, a_j + a) = (a_i - a_j, a_j + a) = |a_i + a - a_j - a|,$$

because $a_i - a_j \mid a_j \mid a$.

Assume now that we constructed a set $\{a_1, \dots, a_N\}$ which is strongly symmetric. Let us construct a strongly symmetric set of cardinality $N + 1$. Let $a = \max_i a_i$ and A be the least common multiple of all natural numbers that are less than or equal to a . Choose $N + 1$ distinct prime numbers p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N, p , all greater than a . By Chinese Remainder Theorem, there is a natural number u such that

$$u \equiv Aa_i \pmod{p_i}$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq N$ and

$$u \equiv p \pmod{A}.$$

By the last condition, $(u, A) = 1$. Therefore, $(u - Aa_i, A) = 1$ for all $i \leq N$. Also, for $i \neq j$ we have $(u - Aa_i, u - Aa_j) = 1$, because for $i \neq j$ we have $|a_i - a_j| \leq a$ so that $a_i - a_j \mid A$ and $(u - Aa_i, a_i - a_j) \mid (u - Aa_i, A) = 1$, hence $(u - Aa_i, u - Aa_j) = (u - Aa_i, A(a_i - a_j)) = 1$. Therefore, Chinese Remainder Theorem guarantees the existence of $k > 0$ satisfying

$$kA^2 \equiv -u \pmod{u - Aa_i} \tag{1}$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq N$. Set now $b_i = Aa_i + kA^2$ for $i \leq N$ and $b_{N+1} = u + kA^2$. We claim that $\{b_1, \dots, b_{N+1}\}$ is a strongly symmetric set. Indeed, the set $\{b_1, \dots, b_N\}$ is strongly symmetric due to our starting observation. Also, all prime factors of $b_i - b_j$ for $i < j \leq N$ are $\leq a$. Further, for any $i \leq N$ we have

$$(b_i, b_{N+1}) = (Aa_i + kA^2, u + kA^2) = (u + kA^2, u - Aa_i) = |u - Aa_i|$$

due to the property 1. Also, $A < p_i \mid u - Aa_i$ and $(u - Aa_i, u - Aa_j) = 1$, which implies that $\{b_1, \dots, b_{N+1}\}$ is indeed strongly symmetric. \square

Now we can prove Lemma 1 and therefore conclude the proof of Theorem 2.

Proof. Assume that \mathbb{G} has N vertices which are labeled by numbers $1, 2, \dots, N$. Let g_{ij} be the (i, j) -th element of the adjacency matrix of \mathbb{G} , i.e., g_{ij} equals 1 if i and j are connected by an edge of \mathbb{G} and 0 otherwise. Let $\{b_1, \dots, b_N\}$ be a strongly symmetric set and for each i and j with $i < j \leq N$ let p_{ij} be some prime such that there is $m_{ij} > 0$ with $p_{ij}^{m_{ij}} \mid b_i - b_j$, $p_{ij}^{m_{ij}+1} \nmid b_i - b_j$ and $p^{m_{ij}} \nmid b_k - b_l$ for all $k < l$ and $(k, l) \neq (i, j)$. Set

$$G = \prod_{i < j} p_{ij}^{1-g_{ij}}$$

and let B be the least common multiple of $\{b_i - b_j\}_{1 \leq i < j \leq N}$. We claim that the induced subgraph of Z on the vertices $b_i + B/G$ is isomorphic to \mathbb{G} . To see this, note that for $i < j$

$$(b_i + B/G, b_j + B/G) = (b_i - b_j, b_j + B/G).$$

Now, if i and j are connected, then both b_j and B/G are divisible by $b_i - b_j$. Indeed, $(b_j, b_i) = |b_i - b_j|$, hence $b_i - b_j \mid b_j$. Also, by the strong symmetry of $\{b_1, \dots, b_N\}$, for all $k > l$ and $(k, l) \neq (i, j)$ we have $p_{kl}(b_j - b_i) \mid [b_k - b_l, b_j - b_i]$. From this we get

$$(b_j - b_i) \prod_{\substack{k < l \\ (k, l) \neq (i, j)}} p_{kl} \mid B$$

and the claim follows. On the other hand, if i and j are not connected, then B/G is not divisible by $b_i - b_j$, as B/G is not divisible by $p_{ij}^{m_{ij}}$. Therefore,

$$(b_i + B/G, b_j + B/G) = |b_i - b_j|$$

if and only if i and j are connected in \mathbb{G} , which means that our induced graph is isomorphic to \mathbb{G} . □

References

[1] W. Banks, P. Pollack, and C. Pomerance, Symmetric primes revisited, *Integers* **19**, #A54.
 [2] P. Fletcher, W. Lindgren, and C. Pomerance, Symmetric and asymmetric primes, *J. Number Theory* **58**, 89-99.
 [3] H. Iwaniec, *Sieve methods*, Graduate course, Rutgers university, New Brunswick, NJ, unpublished notes, 1996.